

A very rare self-assembled ribbon of fused cyclic water pentamers encapsulated in a Cu^{II} based metal-organic framework[†]

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Abstract : A metal organic framework of Cu^{II}, tartarate (tar) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (2,2'-bipy), {[Cu(tar)(2,2'-bipy)]·5H₂O}_n (1) has been synthesized at the mild ambient condition and characterized by single crystal X-ray crystallography. In the compound, the Cu(2,2'-bipy) entities are bridged by tartarate ions which are coordinated to Cu^{II} by both hydroxyl and monodentate carboxylate oxygen to form a one-dimensional chain. The non-coordinated water molecules form 1D water chains by edge-sharing cyclic water pentamers along with dangling water dimers. It shows reversible water expulsion upon heating. The water chains join the 1D coordination polymeric chains to a 3D network through hydrogen-bond interactions.

Keywords : Cu^{II}, tartarate, water ribbons, TGA, XRD.

Introduction

Water is of fundamental importance for human life and plays a vital role in many biological and chemical systems¹⁻³. Water has probably received more scientific and technological interest than any other substance mainly for two reasons – firstly, water is a major chemical constituent of our planet surface and as such it has been indispensable for the genesis of life. Secondly, it exhibits a fascinating array of unusual properties in pure form and as a solvent. Although water is the most profuse compound on earth, it is definitely not a simple liquid. The water chemistry, as regards just the linking of waters by H-bonds to acceptors and donors, is comparable with carbon sp³ covalent chemistry since both have four sites to build networks in a tetrahedral fashion. Water molecules have two hydrogen atoms and two lone pairs enabling them to participate in four hydrogen bonds in a tetrahedral arrangement, but also frequently show 3-coordinate configurations⁴. However, unlike covalent bonds, the H-bond geometry is much more flexible; Krygowski *et al.* described the role of water as a 'gluing factor' in

organic crystals because of its readiness to deform from ideal H-bonded geometry⁵. Water molecule possesses strongly polar hydrogen bonds which are responsible for a striking set of anomalous physical and chemical properties which are thought to be determined by the dynamics and cooperative nature of hydrogen-bonding interactions. Investigations on small water assemblies represent an important method to understand the structural variations and mechanisms in passing from isolated molecules to bulk states and also to understand their role and behavior at a fundamental level⁶. Modern *ab initio* quantum chemistry methods and high-resolution spectroscopy methods have been extremely successful in describing such structures⁷.

Recent studies have led to the characterization of several discrete water clusters (H₂O)_n, where n = 2-10, 12 and 16, in various crystal hosts at room temperature⁸⁻¹³. In contrast to the frequently observed even-membered water ring morphologies such as (H₂O)_n (n = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 18) in solid state complexes, the odd-membered water rings especially, water pentamers are rela-

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

tively rare¹⁴. Theoretical studies predict a cyclic quasi-planar ring structure as the most stable form for water trimer, tetramer and pentamer clusters, while the low-energy structures of larger clusters have 3D cage-like conformations. While these studies have significantly advanced our understanding of the structure of several "discrete" water clusters, very little is known of how these clusters link themselves to form a larger network of water molecules.

Herein, we report the synthesis and crystal structure of a polynuclear compound, $\{[\text{Cu}(\text{tar})(2,2'\text{-bipy})]\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (1) where tar = tartarate. In the structure, highly ordered one-dimensional infinite ribbons of water molecules are stabilized. It is shown that the ribbons consist of a very rare fused cyclic water pentamers along with water dimers.

Experimental

Starting materials :

All the chemicals were of reagent grade and used without further purification. Solvents were dried and distilled prior to use.

Synthesis of the complex :

A solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5 mmol, 1.853 g) in methanol (5 cm^3) was added to an aqueous-methanol (1 : 9 v/v) solution (10 cm^3) of tartaric acid (5 mmol, 0.750 g) followed by triethylamine (10 mmol, 1.4 cm^3) with constant stirring. A methanolic solution (10 cm^3) of 2,2'-bipy (5 mmol, 1.853 g) was added to it. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. A light blue precipitate separated out. The precipitate was filtered, washed with diethyl ether and then redissolved in hot water. The solution was left at room temperature. Light-blue single crystals of $\{[\text{Cu}(\text{tar})(2,2'\text{-bipy})]\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (1), suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by slow evaporation of the blue solution. (Yield : 1.06 g; 70%) *Anal.* Calcd. for. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_{11}$ (457.89) : C, 36.72; H, 4.84; N, 6.12. Found : C, 36.54; H, 4.77; N, 6.19. $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}}/\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) (methanol), 628 (185); IR : $\nu(\text{O-H})$, 3220 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C=O})$, 1584, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C=O})$, 1415.

Crystallographic data collection and refinement :

4537 independent data were collected with Mo $K\alpha$ radiation at 150 K using the Oxford Diffraction X-Calibur CCD System. The crystal was positioned at 50 mm from the CCD. 321 frames were measured with a counting

time of 10 s. Data analysis was carried out with the CrysAlis program¹⁵. The structure was solved using direct methods with the Shelxs97 program¹⁶. The nonhydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were included in geometric positions and given thermal parameters equivalent to 1.2 times those of the atom to which they were attached. Hydrogen atoms bonded to oxygen atoms were located in difference Fourier maps and refined with a distance constraint. An absorption correction was carried out using the ABSPACK program¹⁷. The structure was refined on F2 using Shelx97¹⁶ to R1 0.0400, wR2 0.0794 for 4013 reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$. Data collection and structure refinement parameters and crystallographic data for the two complexes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data of the complex 1

Formula	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_{11}$
Formula weight	457.88
Space group	P212121
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
<i>a</i> (Å)	6.6525(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.2585(10)
<i>c</i> (Å)	18.8653(10)
β (deg.)	91.637(5)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1789.46(18)
<i>Z</i>	4
d_{cal} (g cm^{-3})	1.700
μ (mm^{-1})	1.286
R_{int}	0.0400
No. of unique data	4537
Data with $I > 2\sigma(I)$	4013
R1 on $I > 2\sigma(I)$	0.0413
wR2 on $I > 2\sigma(I)$	0.0744
Goof value	1.061

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. IR spectra in KBr (4500–500 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in water (1200–350 nm) were recorded in a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD) measurements were carried on a Bruker AXS D8 Advance at 50 kV, 40 mA for Cu $K\alpha$ ($k = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), with a scan speed of 1°/min and a step size of 0.02° in 2 h at room temperature. The ther-

mal analysis (TGA-DTA) was carried out on a Mettler Toledo TGA/DTA 851 thermal analyzer in a dynamic atmosphere of dinitrogen (flow rate : $30 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The samples were heated in an alumina crucible at a rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$.

Results and discussion

Structure description of the complex :

The crystal structure of **1** consists of a one-dimensional polymer of $\{[\text{Cu}(\text{tar})(2,2'\text{-bipy})]\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ parallel to the *a*-axis. The ORTEP view is shown together with the atom numbering scheme in the metal coordination sphere in Fig. 1 and the bond distances and angles are

from one tartarate anion and O(35) and O(38) from another. Thus, the tartarates act as tetradentate ligand and connect the metal ions to form a one-dimensional chain (Fig. 1). The carboxylate oxygen atoms O(31) and O(38) of two tartarate moiety occupy the equatorial plane together with the two nitrogen atoms N(11) and N(22) from the 2,2'-bipy ligand. These four equatorial bond lengths are as expected with Cu(1)-N(22) 2.002(2), Cu(1)-N(11) 2.005(2), Cu(1)-O(38) 1.970(2) and Cu(1)-O(31) 1.961(2) Å. By contrast the two axial bonds are significantly longer [Cu(1)-O(34) at 2.335(2) and Cu(1)-O(35) at 2.414(2) Å], partly due to the fact that these two oxygen atoms are protonated and also due to the Jahn-Teller effect.

Fig. 1. ORTEP-3 view of the centrosymmetric unit of **1** with ellipsoids at 30% probability

given in Table 2. In the polymer the copper atoms are six-coordinate being bonded to one chelating 2,2'-bipy ligand together with four oxygen atoms, O(31) and O(34)

The water molecules in **1** are interconnected by a series of hydrogen bonds (Fig. 2) forming ribbon-like chains. The ribbon structure could be viewed as a series of fused

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg.) around the metal centers in complex **1**

Cu(1)-O(31)	1.961(2)	O(31)-Cu(1)-O(38)'	97.21(9)
Cu(1)-O(34)	2.335(2)	O(31)-Cu(1)-N(22)	92.60(10)
Cu(1)-O(38)'	1.970(2)	O(38)'-Cu(1)-N(22)	162.31(9)
Cu(1)-N(22)	2.002(2)	O(31)-Cu(1)-N(11)	163.57(9)
Cu(1)-N(11)	2.005(2)	O(38)'-Cu(1)-N(11)	93.28(9)
Cu(1)-O(35)'	2.414(3)	N(22)-Cu(1)-N(11)	80.76(10)
O(38)'-Cu(1)-O(34)	87.82(7)	O(31)-Cu(1)-O(34)	75.78(8)
O(34)-Cu(1)-O(35)'	151.90(7)	O(38)'-Cu(1)-O(35)'	74.95(7)
N(22)-Cu(1)-O(35)'	91.47(8)	N(22)-Cu(1)-O(34)	108.92(8)
N(11)-Cu(1)-O(35)'	110.61(9)	N(11)-Cu(1)-O(34)	92.08(9)
		O(31)-Cu(1)-O(35)'	84.24(7)

'symmetry operation = $-1 + x, y, z$.

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonding association of the self-assembled chain of water molecules into extended tapes along with dangling water molecules.

pentameric units (Fig. 2) formed by the three of the water molecules, O1W, O2W and O3W. Among them, O1W forms hydrogen bonds to two other water molecules and acts only as hydrogen donor to connect O2W and O3W'. O2W forms hydrogen bonds to three other water molecules and acts as hydrogen acceptor from two water molecules and as donor to one molecule. O3W, on the other hand is acceptor of two H-bonds and donor of two H-bonds and thus is in a tetrahedral geometry. Three of these four H-bonds are the part of cyclic pentamer and the remaining one connects the cyclic pentamer with the water dimer. The repetition of the cyclic water pentamers forms a 1D water chain by sharing the edge formed by O2W-O3W. The dangling water dimer consists of another two water molecules, O4W and O5W, the former one acts as hydrogen acceptor and the later one as hydrogen donor. The dangling water dimers are linked alternately to both side of the pentameric ribbons through hydrogen bonding to O3W. The average O...O distance within the ribbon is 2.795 Å which is slightly shorter than those observed in liquid water (2.854 Å)¹⁸ and com-

parable to those in the ice II phase (2.77–2.84 Å)¹⁹. The O...O distance is comparable to the similar pentameric water chains with Co^{II}-tartarate²⁰. This Co^{II} compound has same composition and structure to the present compound but was prepared under hydrothermal conditions.

In addition, the two O-H groups O(34) and O(35) of tartarate anion that are bonded to the metal form strong donor hydrogen bonds to water molecules O(5W) and O(1W) at 2.688 and 2.642 Å respectively. The two unbonded carboxyl oxygen atoms O(32) and O(37) each act as hydrogen acceptor. O(32) form hydrogen bonds with O(4W) at 2.831 Å and O(5W) at 2.832 Å and O(37) form hydrogen bonds with O(2W) at 2.726 Å. O(4W) also forms a donor hydrogen bond to O(38) at 2.927 Å (Table 3). These hydrogen bonds help to form a 3D metal-organic framework as shown in Fig. 3.

FT-IR spectra of the complex :

The FT-IR spectrum of **1** shows an intense peak for water molecules at 3414 cm⁻¹. The FT-IR spectrum of ice²⁰ shows the O-H stretching at 3220 cm⁻¹, whereas

Table 3. Hydrogen bonds (distances, Å, angles, deg.)

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	<DHA	d(D...A)
O(34)-H(34) O(5W)	0.843	1.861	167	2.688
O(35)-H(35) O(1W)	0.841	1.802	177	2.642
O(4W)-H(1) O(38) [-x+1, y+1/2, -z+3/2]	0.846	2.098	164	2.919
O(4W)-H(2) O(32)	0.839	2.025	161	2.832
O(3W)-H(3) O(2W) [x-1/2, -y+3/2, -z+1]	0.834	1.961	174	2.792
O(3W)-H(4) O(4W) [x+1/2, -y+3/2, -z+1]	0.847	1.944	167	2.774
O(2W)-H(5) O(37) [-x+1, y+1/2, -z+3/2]	0.839	1.912	164	2.728
O(2W)-H(6) O(3W)	0.819	1.976	160	2.761
O(1W)-H(7) O(3W)	0.841	2.000	165	2.820
O(1W)-H(8) O(2W) [x+1/2, -y+3/2, -z+1]	0.843	2.004	170	2.839
O(5W)-H(9) O(4W) [-x, y-1/2, -z+3/2]	0.823	2.055	164	2.856
O(5W)-H(10) O(32) [-x+1, y-1/2, -z+3/2]	0.827	2.011	175	2.836

Fig. 3. 3D framework of complex 1

the stretching vibration in liquid water²⁰ appears at 3490 and 3280 cm^{-1} . Hence, the water chain in 1 shows O–H stretching vibrations for the liquid water. Water clusters identified in other MOFs²¹ show O–H stretching vibrations in the range 3400–3500 cm^{-1} . The O–H stretching vibrations for the hydroxy group of tartarate are obscured by the intense absorption band of water molecule. The strong band at 1584 cm^{-1} is likely to be due to the anti-

symmetric stretching mode of the carboxylate group and the band at 1415 cm^{-1} for the symmetric stretching modes for the carboxylate²².

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The simultaneous TGA-DTA curves of complex 1 reveal that upon heating it starts to lose water molecules at 90 °C and becomes dehydrated at *ca.* 150 °C in a single step (Fig. 4). The observed weight loss (20.5%) corroborates

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric plot showing the weight loss of the sample on increasing the temperature of 1

rates the loss of five water molecules (calc. 19.7%). The dehydrated species reabsorbs exactly five water molecules as is in the original compound on keeping in open atmosphere for several hours (Fig. 5b). This reveals that loss

patterns of the rehydrated species with that of the original one revealed that the metal-organic framework remains more or less the same on deaquation-aquation of the compound (Fig. 7b).

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetric plot of complex 1 showing the loss of water molecules present in (a) complex 1 and (b) rehydrated species of complex 1.

of water molecules occur in a reversible manner without any change in the structure of the coordination polymer. Decomposition of the complex begins at ~ 190 °C.

Powder X-ray analysis :

The crystals of complex 1 was grounded to a powder and examined by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD). The simulated XRPD patterns from single crystal data of complex 1 (Fig. 6) closely match with the experimentally

Fig. 6. Simulated XRPD patterns from single crystal data of complex 1.

observed pattern, shown in Fig. 7a supporting the hypothesis that the bulk powder retains a structural similarity to the single crystal. The similarity of the XRPD

Fig. 7. Experimental XRPD patterns of complex 1 : (a) before water expulsion and (b) after water expulsion.

Conclusions :

We synthesized a one-dimensional coordination polymer of Cu^{II} using 2,2'-bipy and tritartrate ions as ligands simply by mixing the constituents in methanol at ambient temperature. A rare type water chain formed by cyclic water pentamers along with dangling water dimers is stabilized in the compound. The structural data and the cooperative association of the water cluster in the crystal

host may be helpful in the understanding of the stability of water cluster in various natural species including biological assemblies.

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Appendix A

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data for the analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC No. CCDC 757985. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB21EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk). Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.inoche.2006.06.017.

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